

Subsurface Carbon – a General Feature of Noble Metals

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Carbon C_n moieties on late transition metals are historically regarded as poisoning agents for their use in heterogeneous catalysis. Recent experimental studies combining *ab initio* simulations showed the promoting catalytic role of subsurface C atoms in Pd surfaces, *plus* their existence was well established in Ni and Pt surfaces. Here we show, adjoining energetic and kinetic evidences obtained by accurate density functional simulations on surface and nanoparticle models, that such subsurface C species are a general issue to be considered even in coinage noble metal systems. Subsurface C is the most stable situation in densely packed (111) surfaces of Cu and Ag, with sinking barriers low enough to be overcome at catalytic working temperatures. Low-coordinated sites at nanoparticles edges and corners further stabilize them, even in gold, with negligible subsurface sinking barriers. The malleability of low-coordinated sites appears to be the key aspect in the subsurface C accommodation. The incorporation of C species decreases the electron density of the surrounding metal atoms, thus affecting their chemical and catalytic activity. These results broaden the subsurface C chemistry, so as to be considered a general aspect to be regarded in future studies on heterogeneously catalysed processes by late transition metal systems.

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Late transition metals including coinage (Ni, Cu, Ag, Au) and Pt-group (Pt, Pd, Rh, Ir, Re, Os) ones are in widespread use as heterogeneous catalysts^[1] for many reactions of industrial

interest.^[2,3] The systems simplicity, triggered by the applications importance, has prompted research aimed at their catalytic activity improvement, desirably coupled with a materials cost reduction. Nanostructuring strategies have been contemplated for that purpose.^[4,5] The rational design of novel metal and alloy catalysts, backed up by precise *ab initio* quantum chemistry calculations on suited catalyst models, has meant as well a great leap forward in the quest for new, improved activity transition metal catalysts.^[5,6]

Transition metal catalysts are typically employed as shape-defined supported metal nanoparticles (NPs), *e.g.* Au NPs on TiO₂ for low temperature carbon monoxide oxidation,^[3] or Pd NPs on Al₂O₃ for exhaust gas treatments.^[7] The high catalytic performance of such noble metal NPs is inherent to (1) the exposure of facets other than most stable one, and so, chemically more active, and (2) the exhibition of even lower-coordinated sites such as NPs edges and corners, more prone to attach molecules onto.^[8] Other effects can also play a key role, *e.g.* (3) quantum confinement,^[8] (4) strong metal-support interactions,^[9] (5) nanoparticle flexibility,^[10] and (6) nano polymorphism.^[11] Still, the main drawback of such catalysts is that, in the course of the catalysed reaction, these get gradually deactivated over time and use. Besides NP sintering, the origin of this activity loss is the presence of poisoning agents, where carbon excels among others.

Carbon poisoning normally implies C_n moieties, usually generated as a side, undesired product of the on-going catalysed reaction, typically involving organic reagents. At low C coverage, C atoms can strongly adsorb on the catalyst low-coordinated sites, restricting the reagent adsorption upon and/or chemically modifying the very nature of the active sites.^[12-14] At high C coverage, mono- and multilayers of graphene can emerge on top of the metal surface, and even surround and contain metal NPs, structurally fully blocking its active sites.^[15,16] However, recent experiments and computational simulations have changed the paradigm of low C content from a poison to a promoter role, as subsurface C in Pd catalysts favours the selective alkyne hydrogenation to olefins,^[17] and its presence at low-coordination regions of metal NPs is explained by density functional theory (DFT) based simulations.^[14]

Subsurface C has been disclosed to bias the selectivity of other substitutional or interstitial carbon residues,^[18] displaying higher reactivity towards surface O and H adatoms than surface C.^[19] The subsurface moieties mediated chemistry is non-exclusive to Pd. Interstitial C is well-known in Ni surfaces and NPs,^[16] and recently justified on Pt systems,^[20] all belonging to group 10 of the periodic table. Motivated by these results a question mark arises: Is such subsurface atom induced chemistry a singularity or a common feature

otherwise? In the latter assumption, such effect has been often disregarded in the literature, focusing on the vicinal C-perturbing/blocking poisoning picture, which should in fact include the subsurface interaction situation.

Here we show that the existence of subsurface C is a general feature to be considered. This is proven by inspecting its energetic and kinetic stability on most noble metals, namely, group 11 Cu, Ag, and Au. By means of accurate DFT based *ab initio* calculations we give arguments of the competitive, often higher stability of subsurface C compared to surface situations, and its kinetic feasibility by overcoming small subsurface sinking energy barriers, with indications of subsurface C being a near-surface entity. DFT results are obtained on periodic supercell slab models suited to describe single crystal (111) extended surfaces, but also on well-shaped NP models of 79 atoms, a NP size within the scalable regime, and, therefore, representative of larger NPs.^[8] For comparison, the surface and subsurface situations are modelled at the (111) surfaces of the other five face-centred cubic (*fcc*) transition metals. Further details and definitions are present in the Supplementary Information (SI).

The calculated C adsorption (E_{ads}) and absorption (E_{abs}) energies on of Cu, Ag, and Au (111) surface slab models for *hcp* and *fcc* surface, and *tss* and *oss* subsurface sites, which are the most stable sites, are shown in Figure 1. For Cu, the *hcp* and *fcc* sites have similar stability, 436-440 kJ mol⁻¹, but in the subsurface *oss* site C is more stable by 42 kJ mol⁻¹. For Ag, the surface *fcc* site (E_{ads} of 320 kJ mol⁻¹) is 18 kJ mol⁻¹ less stable than the subsurface *oss* site (E_{ads} of 338 kJ mol⁻¹). For Au (111) the surface *fcc* site (E_{ads} of 414 kJ mol⁻¹) is more stable than the subsurface *tss* by 25 kJ mol⁻¹. The main factor for the subsurface stability seems to be a balance between the increased C bonding saturation and the subsurface deformation energetic cost to accommodate C atoms within the constrained subsurface space (see discussion on the deformation energies, E_{def} , and Table S1 in SI). Moreover, the higher chemical activity of gold compared to silver is explained due to a silver deeper *d*-band centre, as found in equivalent DFT simulations,^[21,22] *plus* a weaker C-Ag coupling, which prevents anti-bonding states being above Fermi level, and so, destabilizing the C interaction towards Ag.^[23,24] Estimates at a full monolayer coverage, see Table S6 in SI, show that the surface or subsurface preferential stability prevails, although with reduced E_{ads} and E_{abs} .

A last critical point to tackle is the kinetic hindrance. Subsurface sinking energies displayed in Figure 1 reveal that barriers are within 32 and 63 kJ mol⁻¹ for both Cu and Ag (111) surfaces, and, therefore, non-negligible, yet easy to overcome at the catalyst working

temperatures. For Au (111) the barriers range from 24 to 71 kJ mol⁻¹. The E_{ads} , E_{abs} , and sinking energy barrier values are in line with previous calculations,^[20,25] and here well reproduced for all *fcc* TMs (111) surfaces, see Figure S11 in SI. In addition, the further penetration of the C atom has been also considered yet discarded, see discussion in SI. In general terms group 11 (Cu, Ag, Au) *fcc*→*oss* sinking barriers are comparable yet higher than group 10 (Ni, Pd, Pt), despite of the similar stability of the subsurface C. The kinetic hindrance in the former group could explain the lower experimental solubility of C, see discussion in SI.

The above results go for subsurface C suitability on Cu and Ag surfaces under operating conditions. A remaining aspect towards a more holistic picture view is the C interaction in/on lower-coordinated sites, such as edges and corners of metal. This is fully explored on the (111) facets of M₇₉ metal NP models, see Figure S2 of SI, and E_{ads} , E_{abs} , and subsurface sinking barriers shown in Figure 2. One immediately detects similarities to extended surfaces, with caveats. Many *fcc/oss* and *hcp/tss* sites featuring both surface and subsurface states on Ag₇₉ and Cu₇₉ reveal increased E_{ads} and E_{abs} ranging 32-59 kJ mol⁻¹ for the adsorption situations and 61-72 kJ mol⁻¹ for the absorption situations. For the Au NP the increase of E_{abs} is in general notably higher, 87-100 kJ mol⁻¹, than E_{ads} , 79-83 kJ mol⁻¹. Remaining small size effects and the still close proximity to low-coordinated sites explain the increment of adsorptive situations. In the case of subsurface accommodations, the much larger increment is directly linked to a larger flexibility and deformability of vicinal metal atoms to accommodate and stabilize the subsurface C moiety. This is clearly highlighted by the deformation and attachment energies balance, see Table S2 of SI, where attachment energies can be higher than on the (111) extended surfaces counterparts, by up to 123, 91, and 104 kJ mol⁻¹, for Cu, Ag, and Au NPs, respectively, accompanied by similar deformation energies for surface and subsurface situations. Thus, the low-coordinated sites allow for such deformation, beneficial for the C binding, without compromising the structural energy of the site.

For the Cu₇₉ NP, E_{abs} increases by 209 kJ mol⁻¹ with respect the (111) slab model for corner *tss*, which becomes the most stable site for C on Cu₇₉. Analogous stabilization of subsurface C is observed on edge *tss* on Au₇₉ with an E_{abs} increase of 110 kJ mol⁻¹, with respect to the Au (111) reference. Thus, subsurface C at edge *tss* site becomes the most stable situation in Au₇₉, although only 6 kJ mol⁻¹ more stable than the edge *fcc* location. On Ag₇₉, similarly to Ag (111) surface, the centre *oss* site remains the most stable situation, but only 6

kJ mol^{-1} more stable than the edge *hcp* and *tss* locations. Therefore, low-coordination sites not only preserve the C preference for subsurface in Cu and Ag, but also foster subsurface occupancy even in Au systems. However, at a nearly full coverage situation, see Table S6, the subsurface stability is lost for the NP models, favouring surface situations which can involve the clustering of C atoms, see the example on Cu_{79} as shown in Figure S12 of the SI.

The most prominent feature on all the low-coverage cases is that the energy barriers, E_b , for the subsurface diffusion essentially *vanish*, and so, there is a kinetic free entrance for C adatoms to the subsurface region at the NPs edge and corner regions. Reduced barriers of essentially zero to 17 kJ mol^{-1} are found to occupy corner *tss* and central *oss* sites in Cu_{79} , of 7 kJ mol^{-1} in all situations of Ag_{79} but for the above-commented edge *hcp/tss* case, and a reduced barrier of only 6 kJ mol^{-1} for the entrance towards the edge *hcp* site in Au_{79} . This energy barrier lowering located at under-coordinated sites was also earlier found for Pd NPs.^[14] Moreover, it has been found that low-coordination sites geometrically approach the surface and subsurface minima of the ad/absorbed C atom, see discussion and Figures S3 and S4 in SI.

A further question is whether such subsurface C occupancy would be *thermodynamically* driven. To this end phase diagrams have been acquired for all *fcc* TMs (111) surfaces, considering the turning conditions of pristine surfaces to become early C-containing, either on surface (C^{sur}) or in subsurface (C^{sub}). The details on phase diagrams construction, equivalent to those in literature equalling the chemical potential of C, μ_{C} , to be half of that of acetylene (C_2H_2) minus hydrogen (H_2) molecular gases,^[26] thus emulating alkyne hydrogenation conditions,^[17] are in the SI. The phase diagrams in Figure S9 show that, at regular catalytic temperature working conditions, C atoms would be thermodynamically stable on Rh, Ir, and Pt (111) surfaces, subsurface on Ni and Pd (111) surfaces, and thermodynamically unstable on Cu, Ag, and Au (111) surfaces. This highlights that, on the latter, the isolated C adatom existence would be only dynamically and/or kinetically prompted, and to be considered only on the course of the reaction, even though the final state of such C moieties would be aggregate in graphite or amorphous carbon phases. However, note that the thermodynamic stability is reachable on low-coordinated sites of Cu_{79} NP, see Figure S10. In any case, the *ex situ* subsurface C detection on Cu, Ag, and Au regular surfaces does not seem feasible, and *in situ* a challenging task, *e.g.* see discussion based on ambient pressure X-ray photoemission spectroscopy (APXPS)^[27] in SI, where indirect

approaches through modified surface activity or other surface science techniques seem more feasible for the detection of subsurface C species in noble metal systems.

In any case, to estimate the changes in the electronic structure of the three metals upon adsorption or absorption of C, we calculated the difference between the 3s core levels of metal centers around C and the corresponding centers in the pristine models before C insertion (Table 1 and Table S6). In all cases, there is a stabilization of the metal core level energies, suggesting a decrease of the electron density, hence, a partial positive charge on those metal atoms. The core levels of surface atoms bound to C on Cu and Au (111) surfaces are stabilized by 0.63–0.94 and 0.65–0.89 eV, respectively, while for the Ag (111) surface this interval is 0.27–0.55 eV. For the subsurface atoms this stabilization appears to be smaller, *e.g.* for the *oss* position of the Au slab the energy decrease is 0.65 and 0.13 eV for surface and subsurface Au atoms, respectively. In the same line, the metal reactivity change is measured by the *d* band center shift of the metal atoms bound with the C atom with respect to the same atomic values on the corresponding pristine model. The obtained values reveal the same trend as the 3s core levels (see Table 1 and Table S6). For instance, for Cu, Ag, and Au (111) surfaces with C at *fcc* or *hcp* positions, the shift of *d* band centers to lower energies is 0.90/0.92, 0.40/0.41, and 0.79/0.79 eV, thus making the sites *a priori* less chemically active. The values for the slab and NP models are comparable. Again, the effect of subsurface C is weaker than that of the C atoms on the metal surface.

The density of states (DOS) difference plots for 5*d* states of Au metal centers bound to C at *oss* position of the Au (111) and at *hcp* edge of the NP are shown with solid lines in Figures 3a and 3b, respectively (the DOS plots for Cu and Ag are provided in Figures S5 and S6 of SI). For both slab and NP models there is an increase of DOS in the -7.5 to -4.0 eV region upon C absorption; while, in the -3 to -1 eV region, closer to the Fermi level, a strong depletion of DOS is observed. This picture is in agreement with the stabilization of these metal centers, concluded from the analysis of the previous characteristics. Interestingly, when one considers these metal atoms DOS plots in the same geometry while removing the C atom (see the dashed lines in Figures 3a and 3b), the opposite trend is observed; 5*d* DOS increases strongly close to the Fermi level and decreases at lower energies. Finally, in Figures 3c-f the charge density difference for some of the C-containing Au models is visualized (see also Figures S7 and S8 of SI for the other C positions and metals). These figures confirm that there is a depletion of electron density from the metal centers around C (blue regions) and a

rearrangement of electron density at those centers, likely due to a rehybridization of their frontier orbitals.

In summary, the present findings provide compelling energetic *plus* kinetic evidence that subsurface C species are to be considered in coinage metal systems, from extended surfaces to low-coordinated sites present in metallic NPs, under working catalytic temperature conditions. In the case of low-coordinated sites such as NPs edges and corners, subsurface situations are the most stable situation at low C concentrations, even in gold, to the point of subsurface C being a thermodynamically viable phase in Cu low-coordinated sites. On extended (111) facets/surfaces, subsurface C is dynamically and kinetically envisaged on Cu and Ag systems. These results broaden the subsurface C chemistry, so as to be considered a general aspect of late transition metal systems. The malleability of low-coordinated sites at surfaces, edges, and corners appears to be the key aspect in the subsurface site C accommodation. Furthermore, this aspect does explain the easy sinking of surface C species to near surface situations, with low diffusion energy barriers, from almost vanishing at NPs edges and corners. The experimental *in situ* identification of such C species is challenging, although its presence may explain previously observed peculiar surface chemical activities of coinage metals with C impurities, and, in addition, introduces itself as an aspect to be regarded in the future when studying heterogeneously catalysed processes by transition metal systems. The analysis of electronic structure changes in the C surrounding metal atoms reveals electron deficiency at those centers, indicating a partial positive charge that will affect their chemical and catalytic properties.

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Figure 1. Cu (top image), Ag (middle image), and Au (bottom image) adsorption (E_{ads} , in dark colours) and subsurface absorption (E_{abs} , in light colours) energies, in kJ mol^{-1} , on (111) surface (a) *hcp* and subsurface *tss* sites, respectively, and (b), *fcc* and *oss* sites, respectively. Carbon diffusion energy barriers on each site are shown in black.

Figure 2. Cu₇₉ (top image), Ag₇₉ (middle image), and Au₇₉ (bottom image) C adsorption (E_{ads} , in dark colours) and subsurface absorption (E_{abs} , in light colours) energies, in kJ mol⁻¹, on diverse (111) facet sites. Carbon diffusion energy barriers on each site are shown in black. Dashed lines are present when in-plane situations are found, *i.e.*, adsorption and absorption lead to a common final stable situation (E_{ads} and E_{abs} values are identical).

Figure 3. Difference in the density of states plots of Au 5*d* states for metal centers bound to C and corresponding Au atoms in (a) the pristine model for C in *oss* position on Au (111) surface and (b) C in *hcp* edge position on Au₇₉ NP. Red solid line for surface Au atoms; blue solid line for subsurface Au atoms; dashed lines belong to difference between single point calculations for the corresponding structures after removal of C and the corresponding atoms in the pristine optimized structure: green dashed line belong to surface Au atoms; black to subsurface Au atoms. The plots are normalized with respect to the number of gold atoms around the carbon. Charge density difference for surface *fcc* (c) and subsurface *oss* (d) positions of C on Au(111) slab model; surface *fcc* edge (e) and *oss* edge (f) positions of C on Au NP: green regions indicate the increase of the electron density due to C addition, and blue regions the electron density depletion.

Table 1. Shifts, in eV, of the 3s core levels (positive values correspond to stabilization) and of the d band centers, ϵ_d , of the metal atoms bound to the carbon with respect to the corresponding metal atoms in the pristine (111) slab model.

	3s core level shifts			ϵ_d		
	Cu	Ag	Au	Cu	Ag	Au
<i>fcc</i>	0.94	0.55	0.89	-0.90	-0.40	-0.79
<i>oss</i> Surf	0.63	0.27	0.65	-0.64	-0.24	-0.63
Subs	0.46	0.08	0.13	-0.47	-0.07	-0.13
<i>hcp</i>	0.96	0.56	0.88	-0.92	-0.41	-0.79
<i>tss</i> Surf	0.65	0.30	0.69	-0.65	-0.25	-0.66
Subs	0.61	0.18	0.54	-0.60	-0.11	-0.43

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Ain't Misbehavin': Accurate density functional simulations on suited surface and nanoparticle atomistic models establish the energetic and kinetic feasibility of subsurface C atoms in Cu, Ag, and Au noble coinage metals, so as to be regarded as a key player in surface on-going heterogeneously catalysed processes.

Keywords

Noble Metals • Subsurface Carbon • Extended Surfaces • Metal Nanoparticles • Density Functional Calculations

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